

Monitoring Marine Protected Areas using Data Fusion and AI Techniques

Konstantina Bereta^a, Aristides Millios^b, Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis^a, Dimitris Zissis^c

^aMarineTraffic, Athens, Greece;

^bDalhousie University, Halifax, Canada

^cUniversity of the Aegean, Ermoupolis, Syros, Greece

ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe a workflow for monitoring maritime activity in marine protected areas which makes use of open non-collaborative surveillance data. We developed a workflow that automatically searches for satellite images that cover marine NATURA 2000 areas which are then classified using a Convolutional Neural Network that is able to detect vessels in the areas of interest. Our neural network is trained using AIS data as ground truth.

Keywords: Maritime awareness, AIS, Convolutional Neural Networks, Classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent initiatives by the European Commission study the effect of maritime activities in protected areas, such as NATURA 2000 sites.¹⁻³ In this context, EU working groups, such as the European Economic Interest Group, have published studies aiming at raising awareness regarding the fact that certain maritime activities, such as fishing vessels that carry specific gear can sometimes have a negative impact on the conservation of biodiversity in protected areas (e.g., trawlers can cause damage to corals). Since the effects of vessel activities differ from area to area and depend on the respective species under protection, each EU member state is responsible for establishing its own regulations. In most cases, for each member state, the regulations come at the aftermath of severe loss of biodiversity due to certain maritime activities.

Maritime Situational Awareness (MSA) is defined as the effective monitoring of all activities in the maritime domain that could affect maritime safety and navigation. Sensor based data represent the main pillar of MSA and can be divided into two broad categories: cooperative and non-cooperative systems. Cooperative systems rely on the vessels crews collaboration to identify and report the vessels information, while non-cooperative systems are designed to detect and track vessels that do not provide such information voluntarily.

The most popular Cooperative system, is the Automatic Identification System (AIS) that allows for exchanging messages between ships equipped with AIS transponders, coastal stations and other ships, equipped with AIS receivers. Using AIS, both static and dynamic information about the navigation of vessels can be exchanged. Static messages contain information about the vessel, such as its MMSI, name, type, dimensions, draught, destination, estimated time of arrival, etc. Dynamic messages provide navigational information about the vessel, such as the current position speed, heading, course, and its navigational status. AIS was first introduced in order to enable vessels exchange navigational information with nearby vessels in order to avoid collisions. Since 2004, AIS is considered mandatory for all commercial vessels over 299 Gross Tonnage (GT) and for all passenger vessels regardless of their GT that travel internationally to carry a Class A AIS transponder (which transmits and receives AIS data) aboard. Smaller vessels can also be equipped with a Class B AIS transponder. This resulted in a large amount of information transmitted from vessels all around the world about their navigational status and therefore AIS is considered nowadays as one of the most powerful tools employed to increase the

Further author information: (Send correspondence to K.B)

K.B.: E-mail: konstantina.bereta@marinetraffic.com

A.M.: E-mail: amilios@dal.ca

K.C.: E-mail: konstantinos.chatzikokolakis@marinetraffic.com

D.Z.: E-mail: dzissis@aegean.gr

maritime domain awareness in global scope. Despite the fact that AIS is a valuable source of information, it is often insufficient, as (i) there are areas with limited AIS coverage, (ii) most vessels involved in illegal activities turn off their transponder, and (iii) AIS is mandatory for only certain types of vessels, so there is part of the global fleet that cannot be monitored through AIS.

Non-cooperative systems which are designed to detect and track vessels that do not voluntarily provide information, include coastal and high-frequency (HF) radar, active and passive sonar, ground- or vessel-based cameras (e.g. thermal), and satellite and airborne Earth Observation (EO) systems. EO systems can be divided into optical (generally visual and near-infrared) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems.

Copernicus* is a programme funded by the European Space Agency (ESA) with the aim of sending constellations of new generation satellites, named Sentinels, into orbit in order to monitor the Earth. The Sentinels, in collaboration with global network of thousands of land-, air- and marine-based sensors collect approximately 12 TB of data daily. In this way, Copernicus can be considered as the largest space data provider in the world. Copernicus images are publicly and freely accessible from the Sentinel Data Hub[†] and mirror sites. Sentinel satellites are equipped with different kinds of sensors. Sentinel 1 satellites are a pair of satellites equipped with SAR-C radar, providing high resolution radar images such that they are not affected by weather conditions.

Combining multi-origin information to determine relationships among the data is critical for MSA, as it improves the understanding of a current complex environment. The fusion of data produced by cooperative and non-cooperative systems contributes towards better coverage and robustness to failure, thus improving the reliability and quality of the situational picture.

Our approach is based on the fusion of different data sources, mostly AIS and satellite data, and on the employment of AI techniques such as neural networks. In the context of the work described in this paper, we will integrate AIS information combined with Sentinel 1 images. The motivation of the work described in this paper is the facilitation and automation of data analysis tasks for monitoring marine traffic in protected areas.

2. AUTOMATIC MONITORING OF PROTECTED AREAS USING AIS AND SATELLITE DATA

In this section we describe our prototype implementation that is able to automatically detect vessels in protected areas. In the scope of this paper we only consider NATURA 2000 sites as protected areas but other datasets could be supported as well. In a nutshell, we present a fully automatic approach that is able to monitor protected areas by searching, downloading and classifying images with respect to whether they contain vessels in protected areas. For the classification task, we employed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). For the training task, we implemented a fully automatic workflow which is based on the automatic annotation of satellite images using AIS data.

In this section, we first describe the data sources that are used in our approach, and then we describe in more detail the system architecture and workflows.

2.1 Data sources

A description of the data sources used in our workflow is provided below.

- Europe Coastline. A dataset provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) that contains detailed geometries of the European coastline in shapefile format[‡].
- NATURA 2000 areas. We used a dataset that contains information and geometry boundaries of European NATURA 2000 sites. The dataset is available in Shapefile format by EEA[§]. We refined this dataset using

*<https://www.copernicus.eu/en>

[†]<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>

[‡]<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-coastline-for-analysis-1/gis-data/europe-coastline-shapefile>

[§]<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-10/natura-2000-spatial-data/natura-2000-shapefile-1>

the European boundaries, so we created a dataset that contains only Marine NATURA 2000 sites, i.e., sites that are located in or intersect with the sea.

- AIS data. We used AIS data provided by MarineTraffic[¶]. We used a subset of the attributes provided through AIS from each vessel: the vessel location at the time the satellite image was acquired, the speed, the heading, the course and the vessel type (e.g., cargo, tanker, etc.).
- Satellite images. We used Sentinel 1 images that are available online through the Sentinel Hub^{||}. Sentinel 1 images are equipped with a C-SAR sensor, so it provides radar images in high resolution regardless of the weather conditions.

Figure 1. NATURA 2000 site in the Baltic Sea overlaid by a Sentinel 1 image, depicting vessels, some of which are located inside the protected area visualised in red colour

Figure 1 shows a Sentinel 1 image that covers an area in the Baltic sea. The NATURA 2000 sites located in this area are highlighted in red. Vessels can be seen in the satellite image as white spots. It can be observed that some of them are located into the protected area. AIS can provide auxiliary information about these vessels (e.g., type of vessel, speed, how long it stayed in the area, etc.)

2.2 System Architecture and workflow

Figure 2. High level overview of the system workflow

We have created a system to monitor protected areas using Satellite images and AIS data. The workflow of the system is depicted graphically in Figure 2 and it consists of two main tasks: (a) the offline processing task and (b) the online search and classification task. The workflow of the offline processing task consists of the following steps:

[¶]<http://www.marinetraffic.com/>

^{||}<https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

1. First, Sentinel 1 imagery is downloaded from Sentinel portals, such as the Copernicus Data Hub and it is divided into tiles.
2. Next, a land masking step is performed. This means that all pixels depicting land get removed from the image, so that the reflection of the vessels will not get confused with the reflection coming from the land.
3. Then, the Sentinel image is correlated with AIS data. More specifically, we consider vessel positions that were located in the area depicted in the Sentinel image at approximately the same time that the image was acquired (We use a temporal window of five seconds for that).
4. The output of the correlation step is the automatic annotation of Sentinel image tiles: each image tile in the training set gets labelled with whether it contains a vessel or not.
5. Given the training set produced automatically from the previous step, a Convolutional Neural Network is trained using the Keras framework**. We experimented with a variety of different CNN architectures, and resulted to a CNN that consists of 3 convolutional layers and 2 fully-connected layers, each one followed by a ReLU activation layer. We also used Nadam optimiser, which is a variation of Adam optimiser enhanced with Nesterov momentum. The fully-connected layers are followed by drop-out layers in order to avoid model over-fitting.

The online classification task consists of the following steps:

1. First, the system automatically searches for Satellite images covering areas that overlap with the geographical boundaries marine NATURA 2000 sites. To implement this we use the Sentsat API†. Then, we automatically download the image and the metadata and divide the image into tiles.
2. Next, we proceed with a refinement step in which we filter out the image tiles that are not located in protected areas.
3. Last, each image tile is classified using the trained model produced by the offline processing task.

3. DISCUSSION

One of the main components of our system architecture is the convolutional neural network. Convolutional neural networks are neural networks that are known for their efficiency in classification tasks using images as input, that stems from the fact that they are able to capture relevant features from an image on different levels, in a way that is similar to the human brain. For this reason, there are a lot of efforts in literature that employ CNNs to classify satellite images.⁴⁻¹⁶ The approach described in this paper is built upon these methods.

One of the limitations of the approach described in this paper is the fact the training set is automatically generated by correlating AIS and satellite data. However, vessels with no AIS signal transmitted might appear in the satellite image, creating errors in the automatically created training set, which if not corrected, might create more false negatives in the prediction step. In the context of these work, we used satellite images in areas with good AIS coverage to decrease the number of undetected vessels in the training set by eliminating cases when the vessels are out of coverage (and have not necessarily switched off their transponder on purpose). To eliminate the un-detected vessels in the training set even more, one can use the approach in a semi-automatic way and correct the respective cases manually by examining the tiles that appear to have no vessel.

In the context of this work we used NATURA 2000 dataset and Sentinel 1 images. However, other data sources (e.g., protected areas datasets published by governmental portals) can be used interchangeably. Sentinel 2 images can also be used instead of Sentinel 1 images. Since Sentinel 2 images are optical, instead of radar, they (i) provide more visual information about a vessel (i.e., colour), and (ii) they are able to depict moving objects more accurately, so the processing workflow does not need to take the azimuth shift into account. On the other hand, Sentinel 2 images are not weather-independent, in contrast to the Sentinel 1 images. The efficiency of the proposed workflow can also be improved by using Satellite images from commercial satellites (e.g, micro-satellites) as input.

**<https://keras.io/>

††<https://github.com/sentinel1sat/sentinel1sat>

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we described a fully automatic approach for monitoring protected areas using AIS and satellite imagery. Our approach is based on data fusion from multiple sources (i.e., Sentinel 1 images, AIS, NATURA 2000 sites, European coastline) and also on the implementation of a Convolutional Neural Network that is used to classify the images that cover protected areas.

In future work, we plan to improve our data analysis workflow in order to be able to provide an estimation about the risk associated with the activity of certain vessels in the respective protected areas, taking into account the kinds of species that are protected in each NATURA 2000 site as well as the local regulations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work described in this paper was funded by the EU H2020 project INFORE (Grant Agreement No. 825070).

REFERENCES

- [1] Group, E. E. I., “Overview of the potential interactions and impacts of commercial fishing methods on marine habitats and species protected under the eu habitats directive.” <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/marine/docs/Fisheries%20interactions.pdf> (2013). Online; accessed 11 June 2019.
- [2] Group, E. E. I., “Review of fisheries management measures in natura 2000 sites.” <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/marine/docs/Review%20of%20fisheries%20management%20measures%20in%20Natura%202000%20sites.pdf> (2018). Online; accessed 11 June 2019.
- [3] European Commission, “Guidelines for the establishment of the natura 2000 network in the marine environment. application of the habitats and birds directives.” http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/marine/docs/marine_guidelines.pdf (2007). Online; accessed 11 June 2019.
- [4] Vieira, F. M., Vincent, F., Tourneret, J., Bonacci, D., Spigai, M., Ansart, M., and Richard, J., “Ship detection using SAR and AIS raw data for maritime surveillance,” in *[24th European Signal Processing Conference, EUSIPCO 2016, Budapest, Hungary, August 29 - September 2, 2016]*, 2081–2085 (2016).
- [5] Mazzarella, F., Alessandrini, A., Greidanus, H., Alvarez, M., Argentieri, P., Nappo, D., and Ziemba, L., “Data Fusion for Wide-Area Maritime Surveillance,” (06 2013).
- [6] Guerriero, M., Willett, P., Coraluppi, S., and Carthel, C., “Radar/AIS data fusion and SAR tasking for Maritime Surveillance,” in *[2008 11th International Conference on Information Fusion]*, 1–5 (June 2008).
- [7] Huo, W., Huang, Y., Pei, J., Zhang, Q., Gu, Q., and Yang, J., “Ship detection from ocean sar image based on local contrast variance weighted information entropy,” *Sensors* **18**, 1196 (04 2018).
- [8] Paes, R., Lorenzetti, J., and Gherardi, D., “Ship detection using terra-sar-x images in the campos basin (brazil),” *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, IEEE* **7**, 545–548 (07 2010).
- [9] Grover, A., Kumar, S., and Kumar, A., “Ship detection using sentinel-1 sar data,” *ISPRS Annals of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* **IV-5**, 317–324 (11 2018).
- [10] Mazzarella, F., Vespe, M., and Santamaria, C., “Sar ship detection and self-reporting data fusion based on traffic knowledge,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* **12**, 1685–1689 (Aug 2015).
- [11] Iervolino, P., Guida, R., Lumsdon, P., Janoth, J., Clift, M., Minchella, A., and Bianco, P., “Ship detection in SAR imagery: A comparison study,” (07 2017).
- [12] Achiri, L., Guida, R., and Iervolino, P., “Sar and ais fusion for maritime surveillance,” (09 2018).
- [13] Carthel, C., Coraluppi, S., and Grignan, P., “Multisensor tracking and fusion for maritime surveillance,” in *[2007 10th International Conference on Information Fusion]*, 1–6 (July 2007).
- [14] Lang, H., Wu, S., and Xu, Y., “Ship classification in sar images improved by ais knowledge transfer,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* **PP** (01 2018).
- [15] Stasolla, M. and Greidanus, H., “The exploitation of sentinel-1 images for vessel size estimation,” *Remote Sensing Letters* **7**(12), 1219–1228 (2016).
- [16] Wang, Y., Wang, C., and Zhang, H., “Ship classification in high-resolution sar images using deep learning of small datasets,” *Sensors* **18**, 2929 (09 2018).